

Classroom Management Strategies of Gumaca Catholic Secondary School Teachers: Their Effect on Academic and Behavioral Outcomes of Learners

¹Rachelle A. Atwood, ²Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr.

¹St. Ignatius Parochial School, Inc., ²Marinduque State University

¹rachelleatwood1980@gmail.com, ²leodegariojalos74@gmail.com

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Corresponding Email:

rachelleatwood1980@gmail.com

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Abstract. Classroom management plays a vital role in promoting both academic success and character formation, particularly within faith-based educational institutions. This study examined the classroom management strategies employed by secondary school teachers in Gumaca Catholic Schools Association and determined their effects on learners' academic and behavioral outcomes. Anchored in a values-based educational framework, the research addressed the need to evaluate how Catholic values integration, positive reinforcement, structured routines, and restorative practices contribute to holistic student development. Using a mixed-methods exploratory sequential design, quantitative data were collected through survey questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis, while qualitative data were gathered through open-ended responses and thematically analyzed. Findings revealed that teachers demonstrated a very high level of practice in classroom management strategies (mean = 4.49), consistently integrating faith-based principles and structured approaches. Learners' academic performance was rated very satisfactory (mean = 86.81), and behavioral outcomes were generally positive across value domains. Regression analysis showed that classroom management strategies significantly influenced academic outcomes, explaining 14.4% of the variance, but did not significantly affect behavioral outcomes. Qualitative findings indicated that behavioral concerns were multifaceted, including aggression, disengagement, emotional struggles, and contextual influences such as family environment and technology use, particularly among early adolescents. The study concludes that while structured and values-based classroom management effectively supports academic achievement, behavioral development requires broader, collaborative, and developmentally responsive interventions. These findings contribute to educational practice by informing the development of a Classroom Management Guidebook and reinforcing the importance of holistic approaches in Catholic secondary education.

Introduction

Classroom management is widely acknowledged as a fundamental element of effective teaching and learning, as it directly influences students' academic performance and behavioral development. In today's increasingly diverse and complex educational contexts, teachers are expected to cultivate structured, engaging, and respectful learning environments that respond to varying student needs, technological influences, and evolving learning behaviors. Effective classroom management not only enhances academic achievement but also promotes a positive school climate, minimizes behavioral issues, and supports students' overall well-being (Batool et al., 2023; Jimerson, 2022).

In recent years, the behavioral characteristics of learners have significantly changed, particularly among Generation Z (born 1995–2012) and the Emerging Generation Alpha (born 2013–2025) students. These contemporary learners are highly exposed to digital technologies, interactive media, and fast-paced information, which shape their learning preferences and classroom behavior. While they demonstrate strengths in multitasking and digital literacy, research indicates that they also

tend to exhibit shorter attention spans, decreased persistence in challenging tasks, and increased reliance on external stimulation (OECD, 2022; Twenge, 2023). Furthermore, the post-pandemic educational context has revealed additional concerns such as reduced academic motivation, difficulties in self-regulation, and increased behavioral issues in classrooms (UNESCO, 2021; Dorn et al., 2022). These developments present significant challenges for teachers in maintaining discipline, sustaining engagement, and ensuring effective learning environments.

In response to these evolving learner behaviors, educators have adopted a range of classroom management strategies aimed at promoting order, motivation, and meaningful learning. These strategies include behavior modeling, reinforcement systems, structured routines, and restorative practices, all of which have been shown to positively influence academic performance and reduce classroom disruptions (Simpson et al., 2020; Hashmi et al., 2023). Among these, positive reinforcement, clear expectations, and restorative approaches have been consistently associated with improved student engagement and behavioral outcomes (Owusu et al., 2021; Darling-Hammond et al., 2022). Studies conducted in various educational settings further confirm that these strategies contribute to both academic success and positive classroom behavior (Waweru & Gacheri, 2021).

In faith-based institutions, particularly Catholic schools, classroom management extends beyond maintaining order and discipline. It incorporates moral and spiritual formation, aiming to develop students holistically through the integration of Catholic values such as respect, responsibility, compassion, and integrity. These values-based approaches align with the mission of Catholic education, which emphasizes both academic excellence and character formation. Research suggests that such approaches contribute to improved student behavior, stronger teacher-student relationships, and enhanced engagement (Kumari & Biswas, 2024; Bialik et al., 2022; Nucci et al., 2023). However, integrating values-based instruction with contemporary classroom management strategies presents challenges, particularly in addressing the diverse behavioral tendencies of modern learners.

Despite the growing body of literature on classroom management, much of the existing research focuses on general or public-school settings, often at the elementary level, with limited attention to secondary education and faith-based contexts (Jimerson, 2022; Zoder-Martell et al., 2022). There remains a lack of empirical studies examining how specific classroom management strategies, such as incorporating Catholic values, positive reinforcement, creating routines, and restorative practices, are implemented in Catholic secondary schools and how they influence both academic and behavioral outcomes. Additionally, the challenges encountered by teachers and the coping strategies they employ in managing contemporary learners remain underexplored in these settings.

In the context of the Gumaca Catholic Schools Association, there is a need to investigate how classroom management strategies are practiced and how they respond to the behavioral realities of contemporary learners. Despite the association's commitment to faith-integrated education, limited empirical evidence exists regarding the effectiveness of these strategies and the challenges teachers encounter in their implementation. This highlights the necessity of examining both the strengths and gaps in current classroom management practices.

In response to these gaps, this study aims to determine the classroom management strategies of secondary schools in the Gumaca Catholic Schools Association and examine their effects on learners' academic and behavioral outcomes. Specifically, it investigates the level of practice of classroom management strategies in terms of incorporating Catholic values, positive reinforcement, creating routines, and restorative practices; the level of learners' academic and behavioral outcomes; the significant effect of these strategies on learners' outcomes; as well as the challenges encountered by teachers and the coping strategies, they employ in addressing these challenges.

One of the key outputs of this study is the development of a Classroom Management Guidebook designed specifically for Catholic secondary school teachers. This guidebook is intended to provide a structured, evidence-based, and contextually relevant resource that supports teachers in addressing both academic and behavioral challenges. By consolidating effective strategies into a unified framework, the guidebook aims to enhance consistency, strengthen classroom practices, and promote values-based and restorative approaches to discipline.

Lastly, this study seeks to bridge the gap between theory and practice by providing empirical evidence and practical tools that respond to the needs of contemporary learners. It aims to support teachers in fostering disciplined, engaged, and morally grounded students while promoting academic excellence and holistic development within Catholic secondary schools.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the classroom management strategies of Gumaca Catholic Secondary School Teachers and their effect on learners' academic and behavioral outcomes.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following specific problems:

1. What is the level of practice of classroom management strategies of Gumaca Catholic Secondary School Teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. Incorporating Catholic Values
 - 1.2. Using Positive Reinforcement
 - 1.3. Creating Routines
 - 1.4. Implementing Restorative Practices?
2. What is the level of learners' outcome in terms of:
 - 2.1 Academic Outcomes
 - 2.2 Behavioral Outcomes?
3. Do classroom strategies statistically significantly affect learners' academic and behavioral outcomes?
4. What are the common challenges do secondary school teachers encountered in practicing classroom management strategies?
5. What are the coping strategies that secondary school teachers applied in addressing the challenges they encountered in classroom management strategies
6. Based on the findings of the study, what Classroom Management Guidebook can be developed by the researcher?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-method explanatory sequential research design to comprehensively examine the classroom management strategies of Gumaca Catholic secondary school teachers and their effects on learners' academic and behavioral outcomes. Mixed-methods research integrates both quantitative and qualitative approaches within a single study to provide a more complete understanding of a research problem than either approach alone (Creswell & Creswell, 2023; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The explanatory sequential design is appropriate for the present study because it allows for statistical determination of relationships between variables and subsequent exploration of teachers lived experiences to offer more details about the findings. The quantitative phase of the study utilized a descriptive-regression research design. In this investigation, descriptive statistics were used to determine the level of classroom management strategies in terms of incorporating Catholic values, positive reinforcement, creating routines, and restorative practices, as well as the level of learners' academic and behavioral outcomes. To determine whether classroom management strategies significantly influence learners' outcomes, the study employed multiple linear regression analysis because the study aimed to determine the extent to which the four classroom management strategies predict academic and behavioral outcomes. The independent variables of the study included incorporating Catholic values, positive reinforcement, creating routines, and restorative practices. The dependent variables were learners' academic outcomes and behavioral outcomes. By using multiple regression analysis, the study was able to determine the individual and combined contribution of each classroom management strategy to the identified outcomes. The qualitative phase followed the quantitative analysis and employed a phenomenological research approach. This approach was deemed appropriate because the study aimed to explore the challenges secondary schools encounter in implementing classroom management strategies and the coping mechanisms they employ. Data were gathered through semi-structured interviews to allow participants to share their experiences in depth. The qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, a systematic method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns or themes within qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This method enabled the researcher to organize interview responses into meaningful themes that explained and enriched the quantitative findings.

Respondents/Participants

The study involved secondary school teachers from selected Catholic schools under the Gumaca Catholic Schools Association. The total target population consisted of 186 secondary school teachers across eleven Catholic secondary schools. However, only 111 teachers participated in and completed the survey questionnaire. These 111 respondents constituted the quantitative sample of the study and were considered sufficient for statistical analysis. The respondents were drawn from eleven (11) Catholic schools distributed across six vicariates: the Vicariate of St. Luke, Vicariate of St. Peter, Vicariate of St. Matthew, Vicariate of St. Paul, Vicariate of St. Mark, and Vicariate of St. John. The inclusion of teachers from multiple vicariates ensured broader representation of classroom management practices within the Gumaca Catholic Schools Association. For the quantitative phase, the study employed total enumeration of available respondents. All secondary school teachers within the identified schools were invited to participate in the survey, and those who voluntarily responded comprised the final sample of 111 teachers. For the qualitative phase, nine (9) teachers were selected using purposive sampling. The selected participants met the following criteria: (1) at least three years of teaching experience, (2) direct involvement in classroom management, and (3) willingness to participate in an in-depth interview. The use of nine

participants is consistent with phenomenological research, which typically involves a small number of participants to allow for in-depth exploration of lived experiences.

The inclusion of secondary school teachers as participants was essential because they are directly responsible for implementing classroom management strategies that influence students' academic and behavioral outcomes.

Instrument of the Study

This study utilized both a survey questionnaire and semi-structured interviews to collect data. The survey measured four classroom management strategies—incorporating Catholic values, using positive reinforcement, creating routines, and implementing restorative practices—among secondary school teachers in the Gumaca Catholic Schools Association. To evaluate the effect of these strategies, Learners' academic outcomes were obtained from academic records, while behavioral outcomes were assessed through observed values. To enrich the qualitative findings, semi-structured interviews are conducted with nine purposefully selected teachers from each vicariate to explore the challenges they faced and the coping mechanisms they employed in implementing classroom management strategies.

Procedure

Before collecting data, permission was obtained from the school Superintendent, administrators and teachers of Gumaca Catholic School Association to conduct the study. Participants were informed of the study's purpose and procedures, and informed consent was secured. The survey questionnaires were distributed during the second quarter of the academic year 2025-2026, allowing teachers to reflect on their current classroom management strategies. Completed surveys were collected within a two-month timeframe. For academic performance data, student grades from the previous first and second quarters were gathered to ensure they are aligned with the period of classroom management practices. Records of learners' observed values were gathered. To maintain the confidentiality of both student and teacher information, data were coded to ensure confidentiality and anonymity. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with nine purposively selected teachers to examine implementation challenges and coping mechanisms. Interviews were recorded with consent and transcribed verbatim for analysis. To address ethical considerations, participants were assured that their responses remained anonymous and confidential. The study complied with DepEd's ethical guidelines, ensuring voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any stage.

Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics to address the research questions effectively. To determine the level of classroom management strategies among secondary school Teachers in terms of incorporating Catholic values, using positive reinforcement, creating routines, and implementing restorative practices, responses from the 5-point Likert Scale survey will be analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically mean and standard deviation. The level of academic outcomes was evaluated through the calculation of the mean and standard deviation of student grades using a data retrieval form. Behavioral outcomes were quantified by frequency or counting recorded observed values from data retrieval form. Each scale was supported by corresponding verbal interpretations and qualitative descriptions to ensure clarity and consistency in data interpretation. Examined whether classroom management strategies significantly affect learners' academic and behavioral outcomes, multiple linear regression analysis was utilized. Thematic analysis was applied to examine qualitative responses from teacher interviews using an interview guide, identifying and categorizing patterns and themes related to challenges and coping mechanisms in classroom management.

Results and Discussion

Part I. The Level of Practice of Classroom Management Strategies Among Secondary School Teachers

Indicators	Mean	SD	VD
Incorporating Catholic Values			
I integrate Catholic teachings into my lesson plans and classroom discussions.	4.45	0.657	AP
I encourage students to practice Christian virtues such as kindness, humility, and patience.	4.82	0.471	AP
I begin and end each class with a prayer or spiritual reflection.	4.56	0.683	AP
I incorporate Biblical stories and parables to reinforce moral and ethical lessons in class.	3.96	0.797	OP
I promote the values of service and charity by organizing or supporting student participation in community outreach activities.	4.41	0.719	AP
I emphasize forgiveness and reconciliation as key strategies in resolving classroom conflicts.	4.65	0.550	AP

I encourage students to apply Catholic social teachings in their daily interactions and decision-making.	4.57	0.566	AP
I model ethical behavior by demonstrating honesty, respect, and integrity.	4.67	0.577	AP
I provide opportunities for students to express and deepen their Catholic faith through relevant classroom activities.	4.53	0.644	AP
I foster a classroom environment that respects religious diversity while upholding Catholic values.	4.59	0.595	AP
Composite Mean	4.52	0.626	AP
Using Positive Reinforcement			
I regularly acknowledge and praise students for their efforts and achievements.	4.70	0.515	AP
I use verbal affirmations to encourage positive behavior and academic performance.	4.76	0.490	AP
I provide tangible rewards (e.g., certificates, stickers, or privileges) to reinforce good behavior and academic performance.	4.08	0.833	OP
I implement a point system or behavior chart to monitor and reward students' progress.	4.18	0.855	OP
I emphasize effort and improvement rather than just the final outcomes in assessing student performance.	4.49	0.712	AP
I give constructive feedback that acknowledges students' strengths before addressing areas for improvement.	4.61	0.635	AP
I maintain a supportive classroom atmosphere where students feel safe to express themselves.	4.71	0.529	AP
I celebrate classroom milestones and group accomplishments to promote and sustain positive behavior.	4.59	0.610	AP
I promote peer recognition by encouraging teamwork and appreciation among students.	4.65	0.550	AP
I involve parents in recognizing and reinforcing positive behavior at home.	4.34	0.732	AP
Composite Mean	4.51	0.646	AP
Creating Routines			
I establish daily classroom routines that reflect Catholic values of order, respect, and responsibility.	4.47	0.553	AP
I begin each class with a prayer or spiritual reflection to foster a Christ-centered learning environment.	4.59	0.562	AP
I use visual or written schedules to guide students through both academic activities and religious practices.	4.35	0.683	AP
I use respectful cues or routines for transitions that uphold discipline and attentiveness.	4.51	0.586	AP
I assign student responsibilities (e.g., prayer leaders, materials helpers) to encourage ownership and service, reflecting Catholic social teachings.	4.47	0.796	AP
I involve students in co-creating classroom routines that are aligned with Gospel values of respect, cooperation, and responsibility.	4.33	0.705	AP
I include regular times in the schedule for reflection, silent reading, or values integration activities.	4.17	0.830	OF
I adjust routines when needed to address the diverse academic, spiritual, and cultural needs of my students.	4.41	0.707	AP
I reinforce routines to promote both behavioral order and positive character formation, as emphasized in Catholic education.	4.52	0.658	AP
I maintain a balance between structured routines and flexibility to accommodate both learning needs and spiritual growth.	4.52	0.658	AP
Composite Mean	4.44	0.674	AP
Implementing Restorative Practices			
I promote open dialogue to resolve conflicts and build a supportive, Christ-centered classroom environment.	4.51	0.616	AP
I use restorative conversations or circles to foster mutual respect, healing, and accountability among students.	4.31	0.711	AP
I conduct individual discussions with students involved in behavioral issues to understand their perspective and repair relationships.	4.31	0.760	AP
I involve students in collaboratively solving conflicts and reflecting on the impact of their actions.	4.42	0.668	AP
I prioritize restoring relationships and forgiveness over assigning punishments for misbehavior.	4.55	0.748	AP
I guide students in developing empathy by helping them understand how their actions affect others in the school community.	4.64	0.615	AP
I provide regular opportunities for students to reflect on their behavior and take responsibility in a non-punitive setting.	4.45	0.697	AP
I collaborate with parents or guardians as part of the restorative process when addressing repeated or serious behavioral issues.	4.36	0.840	AP

I establish clear guidelines for respectful communication and peaceful conflict resolution, guided by Gospel values.	4.57	0.627	AP
I ensure that every student feels heard and valued in discussions about classroom behavior.	4.75	0.495	AP
Composite Mean	4.49	0.678	AP
GRAND MEAN	4.49	0.656	AP

Table 1. Level of practice of classroom management strategies of secondary school teachers in terms of incorporating catholic values, using positive reinforcement, creating routines, implementing restorative practices

The findings reveal that secondary school teachers demonstrate a very high level of practice of classroom management strategies across all measured dimensions, as evidenced by the overall grand mean of 4.49 (SD = 0.656), interpreted as always practiced. This indicates that classroom management in the participating Catholic secondary schools is deeply embedded in both pedagogical routines and faith-based educational principles. The consistently high means and relatively low standard deviations across indicators further suggest a strong degree of consensus among teachers regarding the regular implementation of these strategies.

In terms of incorporating Catholic values, the composite mean of 4.52 (SD = 0.626) reflects a sustained and systematic integration of faith-based principles into instructional practice. Teachers consistently embed Catholic teachings, Christian virtues, prayer, moral reflection, and ethical modeling into classroom life. High ratings on encouraging virtues, modeling ethical behavior, and emphasizing forgiveness indicate that classroom management extends beyond behavioral regulation toward holistic character formation. The slightly lower mean for integrating Biblical stories, though still within the “Often Practiced” range, suggests minor variability in instructional approaches but does not detract from the overall strong faith integration. These results affirm the centrality of Gospel-centered pedagogy in shaping both the moral and academic climate of Catholic secondary education.

Regarding positive reinforcement, the composite mean of 4.51 (SD = 0.646) likewise falls within the “always practiced” category, highlighting a classroom culture grounded in affirmation, encouragement, and constructive feedback. Teachers consistently acknowledge effort, celebrate achievements, and foster supportive environments where students feel safe and valued. While tangible reward systems and behavior charts received comparatively lower—though still high—ratings, the stronger emphasis on verbal affirmations, effort-based recognition, and peer appreciation reflects a shift toward intrinsic motivation rather than purely extrinsic reinforcement. This aligns with contemporary motivational theories that advocate for supportive teacher–student relationships as foundational to sustained academic engagement and positive behavior.

In the dimension of creating routines, the composite mean of 4.44 (SD = 0.674) indicates that structured and value-oriented classroom systems are firmly established. Teachers consistently implement prayerful beginnings, orderly transitions, defined responsibilities, and reflective practices. The integration of routines with Catholic social teachings demonstrates that structure is not merely procedural but formative, cultivating responsibility, cooperation, and spiritual growth. The slightly lower mean for scheduled reflection or silent reading suggests opportunities for strengthening contemplative practices; nevertheless, routines are clearly institutionalized as mechanisms for maintaining order while nurturing moral development.

Similarly, restorative practices obtained a composite mean of 4.49 (SD = 0.678), signifying that restorative and relational approaches are consistently applied. Teachers prioritize dialogue, empathy, accountability, and forgiveness over punitive measures, reinforcing a Christ-centered framework of reconciliation and community building. High ratings on ensuring that students feel heard and valued underscore a relational model of discipline rooted in dignity and mutual respect. This approach reflects alignment with restorative justice principles and Catholic educational philosophy, emphasizing healing, responsibility, and the restoration of relationships within the school community.

These results demonstrate that classroom management among secondary school teachers is not limited to maintaining discipline but is holistically oriented toward faith formation, character development, positive motivation, structured learning, and relational restoration. The uniformly high levels of practice across dimensions indicate a coherent and values-driven management framework that integrates spiritual, behavioral, and academic objectives. Such findings suggest that Catholic secondary schools have successfully institutionalized classroom management strategies that foster both academic excellence and moral formation, reinforcing the distinctive identity and mission of Catholic education.

The results in Table 2 revealed that secondary school teachers demonstrated a very high level of practice of classroom management strategies, with an overall grand mean of 4.49 (Always Practiced). This finding indicates that teachers consistently integrate faith-based and pedagogical strategies such as incorporating Catholic values, positive reinforcement, creating routines, and restorative practices in managing their classrooms.

This finding supports the literature that emphasizes the importance of structured and consistent classroom management in maintaining a positive learning environment. According to Zhu and Liu (2023), structured classroom management strategies significantly increase student engagement and reduce classroom disruptions. Similarly, Koutrouba (2020) highlighted that teachers who establish clear expectations and maintain consistent discipline practices are more effective in managing student behavior. The high level of classroom management practice observed in the study therefore confirms the assertion that well-structured management practices contribute to effective teaching and learning.

The strong integration of Catholic values (Composite Mean = 4.52) aligns with the findings of Sihotang and Sijinjak (2024), who emphasized that values-based education in Catholic institutions plays a significant role in shaping both student discipline and moral development. Likewise, Xu et al. (2023) found that integrating faith-based principles in classroom management strengthens teacher–student relationships and improves classroom engagement. The results of the present study confirm these claims, indicating that teachers actively embed spiritual and moral teachings into daily classroom practices.

Furthermore, the emphasis on positive reinforcement (Composite Mean = 4.51) supports the findings of Rafi et al. (2020), who identified praise, feedback, and recognition as the most commonly used reinforcement strategies in classroom management. Similarly, Yousuf (2023) found that positive reinforcement strategies such as recognition and encouragement significantly improve student motivation and engagement. However, the present study shows that teachers rely more heavily on verbal affirmations and encouragement rather than tangible rewards, which is consistent with the findings of Owusu et al. (2021), who cautioned against overdependence on external rewards and recommended promoting intrinsic motivation among students.

The high level of implementation of classroom routines (Composite Mean = 4.44) also confirms the conclusions of Atmaja (2024) and Haydon et al. (2021), who emphasized that structured routines help reduce classroom disruptions and improve student participation. Similarly, Khan et al. (2021) found that clear schedules and structured classroom transitions increase learning efficiency and classroom discipline. The findings of the present study therefore reinforce the role of routine establishment in maintaining an organized and conducive learning environment.

Likewise, the consistent practice of restorative practices (Composite Mean = 4.49) supports the findings of Forsberg and Leko (2021), who argued that restorative approaches promote accountability, strengthen relationships, and foster a supportive classroom environment. Similarly, Weber et al. (2021) found that restorative practices improve classroom climate and social inclusion among students. The emphasis on dialogue, empathy, and reconciliation observed in the present study reflects the restorative discipline philosophy commonly practiced in Catholic educational institutions.

Overall, the results confirm the literature suggesting that effective classroom management in Catholic schools is values-driven, structured, and relational, integrating both academic and moral formation. This finding is consistent with Bual and Madrigal (2021), who found that a supportive school climate and strong teacher leadership significantly contribute to effective classroom management in Catholic schools.

Part II. The Level of Learners' Outcome

Academic Outcome	Frequency	Percentage
Did Not Meet Expectation	0	0.00
Fairly Satisfactory	0	0.00
Satisfactory	21	18.9
Very Satisfactory	70	63.1
Outstanding	20	18.0
Total	111	100.0
Mean	86.81	
SD	2.620	
Verbal Description	Very Satisfactory	

Table 2. Level of learners' outcome in terms of academic outcomes

The results indicate that learners demonstrate a generally high level of academic outcomes. The overall mean of 86.81 (SD = 2.620), interpreted as very satisfactory, reflects strong and consistent academic performance of learners taught by 111 teachers. A substantial majority attained performance levels within the upper proficiency categories, with no learners falling into the lower performance brackets. The relatively low standard deviation further suggests limited variability in

academic achievement, indicating homogeneity in performance and a stable level of instructional effectiveness across the sample. These findings imply that learners are meeting, and often exceeding, expected academic standards, which may be associated with structured instructional practices and supportive classroom environments.

The findings in Table 3 revealed that learners demonstrated very satisfactory academic outcomes, with a mean score of 86.81 and most students categorized under Very Satisfactory (63.1%) and Outstanding (18%). These results indicate that learners consistently perform above the expected academic standards. This finding supports the study of Freeman et al. (2014), which found that active and well-managed classroom environments significantly improve student performance and reduce academic failure rates. The results also align with the research of Safiullah et al. (2023), who concluded that effective classroom management enhances student engagement and contributes to improved academic achievement.

Similarly, the findings support the work of Dumaguing and Yango (2023), who reported that teachers with strong classroom management competencies tend to have students who achieve higher academic performance. The present study further reinforces this claim, suggesting that structured teaching practices and effective behavior management strategies contribute to stable and consistent academic outcomes.

The results also correspond with studies on private and Catholic schools. For instance, Bernal et al. (2020) found that students in private schools often demonstrate higher academic performance due to smaller class sizes, structured learning environments, and higher expectations from teachers. Likewise, Ajayi (2024) emphasized that private educational institutions often provide conditions that support better academic achievement, including improved teacher–student interactions and well-organized learning environments.

However, the findings also reflect the argument of Gruijters et al. (2021) and Larsen et al. (2020) that academic success is not solely determined by the type of school but also by factors such as parental involvement, learning resources, and socioeconomic background. While classroom management contributes to improved outcomes, other contextual factors also influence academic performance.

Level of Learners' Outcome in terms of Behavioral Outcomes

Behavioral Outcomes	Frequency	Percentage
Maka-Diyos		
Not Observed	0	0.00
Rarely Observed	0	0.00
Sometimes Observed	26	23.4
Always Observed	85	76.6
Total	111	100.0
Mode	Always Observed	
Makatao		
Not Observed	0	0.00
Rarely Observed	0	0.00
Sometimes Observed	43	38.7
Always Observed	68	61.3
Total	111	100.0
Mode	Always Observed	
Makabansa		
Not Observed	0	0.00
Rarely Observed	0	0.00
Sometimes Observed	43	38.7
Always Observed	68	61.3
Total	111	100.0
Mode	Always Observed	
Makabayan		
Not Observed	0	0.00
Rarely Observed	0	0.00
Sometimes Observed	57	51.4
Always Observed	54	48.6
Total	111	100.0
Mode	Sometimes Observed	

Table 3. Level of learners' outcome in terms of behavioral outcomes

The results indicate that learners demonstrate a generally high level of behavioral outcomes. Learners demonstrate positive behavioral manifestations in all four core value domains with respect to behavioral outcomes. In the dimension of Maka-Diyos, the majority of learners were reported as “always observed,” indicating consistent demonstration of faith-oriented behaviors such as respect for spiritual practices and reverence in daily conduct. Similarly, in the Makatao and Makabansa dimensions, most learners were also categorized as “always observed,” reflecting strong adherence to values related to respect for others, social responsibility, and national identity. These results suggest that learners consistently embody interpersonal sensitivity, civic awareness, and socially responsible behavior within the school context.

However, in the Makabayan dimension, the modal response shifted to “sometimes observed,” with responses more evenly distributed between “sometimes” and “always.” This pattern indicates comparatively moderate consistency in demonstrating patriotic engagement and participatory citizenship behaviors. While still positive overall, this finding suggests that nationalistic expression and active civic participation may require further reinforcement through curricular integration and experiential learning opportunities.

Collectively, the findings revealed that learners exhibit very satisfactory academic performance alongside consistently positive behavioral dispositions, particularly in faith-based and interpersonal domains. The convergence of high academic achievement and strong value-oriented behavior reflects an educational environment that fosters both cognitive development and character formation. Nonetheless, the comparatively moderate expression of patriotic behaviors highlights an area for potential pedagogical enhancement to ensure balanced development across all value dimensions. The results of Table 4 show that learners generally demonstrate positive behavioral outcomes, particularly in the domains of Maka-Diyos, Makatao, and Makabansa, where the majority of students were categorized as Always Observed. This suggests that students consistently demonstrate behaviors aligned with spiritual values, respect for others, and social responsibility.

These findings support the research of Siddique (2020), who found that students exposed to religious education tend to demonstrate higher levels of honesty, altruism, and moral behavior. Similarly, Muderredzwa (2021) found that moral education in Catholic schools promotes responsibility and ethical decision-making among students.

The findings also align with Patampang et al. (2024), who concluded that positive school climate and strong teacher guidance in Catholic schools significantly influence student behavior. Likewise, Ginting et al. (2022) emphasized that teachers who maintain strong relationships with students help foster positive behavioral outcomes.

However, the relatively moderate results in the Makabayan dimension, where the modal response was Sometimes Observed, contrast with the findings of Age and Dhey (2024), who suggested that narrative-based teaching strategies significantly enhance civic awareness and patriotic values among students. This difference may indicate that while faith-based and interpersonal values are strongly emphasized in Catholic schools, civic participation and national identity may require stronger curricular reinforcement.

Part III. Effect of Classroom Management Strategies to Learners' Academic and Behavioral Outcomes

Model	Coefficients ^a			t	p-value	Decision
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	1.345	.619		2.172	.032	Reject Ho
1 Management Practices	.602	.140	.380	4.290	.000	

Dependent Variable: Academic Outcomes

Model: R = .380^a, R² = .144(14.4%), Std. Error = .56722

Predictors: (Constant), Teacher's Classroom Management Practices

Regression equation model: y₁ = 1.345 + .602(Classroom Management Practices) + .56722(std. error)

Table 4. Statistical table showing the effect of classroom management strategies to learners' academic outcome

Similarly, Sultmann et al. (2024) observed that students often understand ethical values theoretically but may struggle to translate them into real world civic engagement. This observation supports the current finding that patriotic behaviors may need more experiential and community-based learning activities.

The results of the regression analysis indicate that teachers' classroom management practices exert a statistically significant positive effect on learners' academic outcomes. The model yielded a moderate correlation coefficient ($R = .380$), suggesting a meaningful association between classroom management strategies and academic performance. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .144$) reveals that approximately 14.4% of the variance in learners' academic outcomes can be explained by teachers' classroom management practices. While this proportion indicates that other factors also contribute to academic achievement, it nonetheless confirms that classroom management constitutes a substantive and measurable predictor within the instructional context.

The unstandardized regression coefficient ($B = .602$) demonstrates that for every one-unit increase in the level of classroom management practices, learners' academic outcomes increase by .602 units, holding other factors constant. The standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = .380$) further reflects a moderate positive effect size. The computed t-value ($t = 4.290$) with a p-value less than .001 indicates that the relationship is highly significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This confirms that effective classroom management strategies significantly enhance learners' academic performance.

The regression equation ($y_1 = 1.345 + .602[\text{Classroom Management Practices}]$) suggests that even at baseline levels of management practices, learners demonstrate a foundational level of academic outcomes, which is further strengthened as management effectiveness improves. These results show how important structured routines, proactive behavior management, clear expectations, and consistent disciplinary practices are for creating a learning-friendly environment. From a theoretical perspective, the results align with classroom ecology and instructional management frameworks, which posit that well-managed classrooms maximize instructional time, reduce disruptive behaviors, and increase academic engagement.

Generally, the findings affirm that classroom management is not merely a behavioral control mechanism but a strategic pedagogical practice that directly contributes to improved academic outcomes. Strengthening teachers' competencies in classroom management may therefore serve as a viable intervention for enhancing learner achievement, particularly within public elementary school settings.

This finding strongly supports the study reviewed by Batool et al. (2023), effective classroom management strategies such as praise, structured routines, and group engagement significantly improve student motivation and academic performance. Similarly, Owusu et al. (2021) found that reinforcement strategies positively correlate with academic achievement among students.

The results also align with Jimerson (2022), who reported that reducing off-task behaviors through structured classroom management improves students' academic success. Likewise, Afalla and Fabelico (2020) concluded that structured learning environments contribute to sustained academic achievement.

However, the relatively moderate explanatory power ($R^2 = 14.4\%$) indicates that while classroom management contributes to academic performance, other factors also play significant roles. This finding supports Gruijters et al. (2021), who emphasized that student background, parental support, and school resources also influence academic outcomes.

Statistical Table Showing the Effect of Classroom Management Strategies to Learners' Behavioral Outcomes

Model	Coefficients ^a		t	p-value	Decision
	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Beta			
(Constant)	2.742	.448	6.118	.000	Do not Reject Ho
1 Management Practices	.193	.102	1.904	.060	

Dependent Variable: Behavioral Outcomes

Model: $R = .179$, $R^2 = .032(3.2\%)$, Std. Error = .41064

Predictors: (Constant), Teacher's Classroom Management Practices

Table 5. Statistical table showing the effect of classroom management strategies to learners' behavioral outcomes

The regression analysis results indicate that teachers' classroom management strategies do not exert a statistically significant effect on learners' behavioral outcomes at the conventional 0.05 level of significance. The model yielded a weak positive correlation ($R = .179$), suggesting only a minimal association between classroom management practices and students' behavioral outcomes. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .032$) shows that classroom management strategies account for approximately 3.2% of the variance in learners' behavior, reflecting a minimal explanatory power and indicating that the majority of behavioral variations are influenced by other factors beyond classroom management alone. The unstandardized regression coefficient ($B = .193$) suggests that increases in classroom management practices are associated with slight improvements in behavioral outcomes. However, the computed t-value ($t = 1.904$) and corresponding p-value (.060) exceed the 0.05 threshold, leading to the decision not to reject the null hypothesis. While the standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = .179$) indicates a positive direction of influence, the effect size remains weak and statistically non-significant. This implies that, although better management practices may be associated with improved behavior, the relationship is not strong enough to establish a definitive predictive effect in the present sample.

These findings suggest that learners' behavioral outcomes may be shaped by a broader constellation of variables, including family background, peer influence, school climate, socio-emotional competencies, and institutional disciplinary policies. From a theoretical perspective, while classroom management is widely recognized as a preventive and regulatory mechanism within instructional settings, behavior development is multidimensional and extends beyond the immediate classroom context.

Overall, the results highlight that classroom management strategies alone may not be sufficient to significantly influence learners' behavioral outcomes. Comprehensive behavioral interventions that integrate teacher practices with school-wide positive behavior support systems, guidance programs, and parental involvement initiatives may therefore be necessary to produce more substantial and statistically meaningful improvements in student behavior.

Contrary to expectations, the results revealed that classroom management strategies did not significantly affect learners' behavioral outcomes ($p = .060$).

This finding contrasts with several studies in the literature. For example, Nafisah et al. (2020) found that structured classroom management strategies significantly improve student behavior in 77.8% of the studies reviewed. Similarly, Oparaugo et al. (2024) reported a strong relationship between effective classroom management and positive student behavior.

However, the findings of the present study align with Durisic (2022), who argued that student behavior is influenced not only by classroom practices but also by factors such as school climate, peer relationships, and family background. Likewise, Lynch et al. (2020) suggested that behavioral development is shaped by broader institutional policies and community influences beyond classroom management alone.

Furthermore, Kapembwa et al. (2021) noted that the effectiveness of behavioral interventions often depends on school-wide discipline programs rather than individual teacher practices alone. This may explain why classroom management strategies in the present study had limited statistical influence on behavioral outcomes.

Overall, the results of the study confirm that secondary school teachers consistently implement classroom management strategies aligned with Catholic educational principles. These strategies contribute significantly to learners' academic success, supporting previous research that emphasizes the role of structured classroom environments in improving student achievement.

However, the findings also reveal that behavioral outcomes are influenced by multiple factors beyond classroom management, including school climate, family background, and institutional policies. This suggests that while teachers play a crucial role in shaping student behavior, broader systemic support is necessary to achieve more substantial behavioral improvements.

The results therefore highlight the importance of integrating classroom management practices with school-wide character formation programs, guidance services, and parental involvement initiatives to promote holistic learner development in Catholic secondary schools.

Part IV. Common Challenges of Secondary Schools Encountered in Classroom Management Strategies

Respondent Code	Raw Response	Initial Code	Category	Final Theme
T1	"Most common challenges in managing student behavior and dealing with different types of disruptive behaviors like making noise on throwing small objects, short attention span (not paying attention in class) and bullying or teasing other students."	Noise-making; throwing objects; short attention span; bullying; teasing	Disruptive Behavior; Inattention; Peer Conflict	Classroom Disruption and Peer-Related Misconduct
T2	"Marami sa mga estudyante ay madaling mang 'bully' sa kapwa mag-aaral: Nagkukulitan; Dahilan upang mag-ingay ang mga mag-aaral sa loob ng silid-aralan."	Bullying; playful teasing; noise inside classroom	Peer Misconduct; Classroom Noise	Classroom Disruption and Peer-Related Misconduct
T3	"The most common challenges I encountered in managing students behavior is being clumsy. Also, they are not serious in their studies." "The most common challenges in managing student behavior I encountered is that students may don't like to serious how I manage their behavior since they repeated if most of the time."	Carelessness; lack of seriousness; low academic commitment	Low Academic Motivation	Student Disengagement and Lack of Academic Focus
T4	"Well, I've encountered a lot of challenges in managing student behavior, especially with students who are so stubborn that they won't let the teacher talk to them. They have their own worlds..."	Repeated misbehavior; resistance to discipline	Non-compliance; Repetitive Behavior	Resistance and Repeated Rule Violations
T5	"One of the most common challenges... lack of motivation academic, short attention span, and differences between home and school values..."	Stubbornness; refusal to listen; individualized differences	Defiance; Individual Differences	Resistance and Behavioral Defiance
T6	"Maintaining students attention during lessons, handling disruptive behaviors and addressing differences in learning pace..."	Low motivation; short attention span; value conflict	Engagement Issues; Home-School Gap	Student Disengagement and Environmental Value Conflict
T7	"Students with emotional or mental health issues because of personal problems, peer influence and pressure, frequent use of gadget, distractions in classes, disruptive late comers."	Attention difficulty; disruption; varied learning pace; low participation	Inattention; Learning Differences	Challenges in Sustaining Student Engagement
T8	"Maintaining order, the learners inappropriate gestures, talking with their friends and classmates, not complying with homeworks and projects."	Emotional issues; peer pressure; gadget use; lateness	Emotional Concerns; External Influences	Emotional and External Environmental Challenges
T9		Inappropriate gestures; talking; non-compliance; unfinished work	Disruption; Task Non-compliance	Classroom Disruption and Academic Non-Compliance

Table 6. Common challenges secondary school teachers encountered in practicing classroom management strategies

The thematic analysis identified four major themes: (1) Classroom Disruption and Peer-Related Misconduct, (2) Student Disengagement and Lack of Academic Focus, (3) Resistance and Repeated Rule Violations, and (4) Emotional and Environmental Influences on Behavior.

The most prominent theme is Classroom Disruption and Peer-Related Misconduct. Most respondents (T1, T2, T7, T9) reported behaviors such as noise-making, teasing, bullying, inappropriate gestures, and talking during class. These actions interrupt the flow of instruction and make it difficult for teachers to maintain order and sustain students' attention.

The second key theme is Student Disengagement and Lack of Academic Focus. Several teachers (T3, T6, T7) observed low motivation, short attention spans, lack of seriousness toward academic tasks, and limited participation. These findings suggest that teachers face not only active misbehavior but also passive forms of disengagement that hinder learning. Another important theme is Resistance and Repeated Rule Violations (T4, T5). Teachers described some students as stubborn, unresponsive to corrective measures, and likely to repeat the same misbehavior. This reflects challenges in maintaining consistency, discipline, and authority in the classroom.

The final theme, Emotional and Environmental Influences on Behavior (T6, T8), points to factors such as mental health concerns, peer pressure, gadget distractions, and differences between home and school values. These responses show that student behavior is shaped by external and psychological influences that are often beyond the teacher's control.

Overall, the findings indicate that classroom management involves addressing both visible disruptions and deeper underlying issues. Behaviors such as noise, teasing, and non-compliance may be surface-level expressions of broader challenges related to engagement and self-regulation. Low motivation and limited attention suggest that behavior management should not rely solely on rules and discipline but must also include strategies that promote active participation and interest.

Repeated misconduct and resistance to discipline may indicate gaps in consistency or reinforcement practices. Furthermore, emotional and home-related influences highlight the complexity of classroom management, as teachers must navigate not only behavioral concerns but also developmental, psychological, and environmental factors affecting learners. The findings of the thematic analysis strongly align with existing literature on classroom management challenges in secondary education. The identified themes reflect both local and international research, reinforcing the consistency of issues encountered by teachers across different contexts.

The theme Classroom Disruption and Peer-Related Misconduct corresponds with the findings of Riola (2024), who identified student behavioral issues as a major barrier to effective classroom management. Similarly, studies by Khasinah et al. (2024) and Omodan and Mamaile (2024) emphasize that disruptive behaviors, including peer-related conflicts and lack of discipline, significantly affect instructional flow and classroom control. This supports the current study's observation that noise-making, teasing, and bullying interfere with teaching and learning processes.

The second theme, Student Disengagement and Lack of Academic Focus, is consistent with Xu et al. (2023), who found that discomfort and lack of engagement in learning tasks contribute to classroom management difficulties. Likewise, Khasinah et al. (2024) highlighted student motivation and psychological conditions as key internal factors influencing behavior. The present findings, which include low participation and limited attention spans, reinforce the idea that disengagement is a critical but often less visible classroom management concern.

The theme Resistance and Repeated Rule Violations supports the findings of Iqbal et al. (2021), who noted that difficulties in establishing rapport and clear expectations can lead to non-compliance among students. The repeated misbehavior described by teachers in this study also reflects challenges in consistency and reinforcement, which were identified as key issues in both foreign and local studies. Furthermore, Bual (2021) noted that less experienced teachers may struggle more with enforcing rules effectively, which may contribute to persistent behavioral issues.

The final theme, Emotional and Environmental Influences on Behavior, aligns with multiple studies emphasizing external and psychological factors affecting student behavior. Khasinah et al. (2024) identified psychological conditions as a major internal factor, while Mamaile and Omodan (2023) highlighted the impact of parental involvement and home environment. In the Philippine context, Hungo et al. (2023) and Bual and Madrigal (2021) further emphasized how institutional and environmental factors, such as school climate and administrative demands, influence classroom management. The current study's findings on mental health concerns, peer pressure, and home-school value differences strongly support these conclusions.

Overall, the study confirms that classroom management challenges are multifaceted, involving behavioral, motivational, relational, and environmental dimensions. The findings extend existing literature by demonstrating that both active disruptions and passive disengagement must be addressed simultaneously. Moreover, the persistence of these issues across studies suggests that effective classroom management requires a holistic approach that integrates discipline strategies, student engagement techniques, emotional support, and institutional backing.

Part V. Coping Strategies that Secondary School Teachers Applied in Addressing the Challenges They Encountered in classroom management strategies

Respondent Code	Raw Response	Initial Code	Category	Final Theme
T1	"To address common behavior problems... it must be done directly, privately and specifically... listen to students concerns and be firm but fair."	Private correction; listening; firmness; fairness	Respectful Discipline	Private and Respectful Behavior Correction
T2	"Pinupuntahan ko ang mga bata... kakausapin... pinakikinggan... pagbatiin sila... pinapadalhan ng sulat ang mga magulang..."	Private conversation; mediation; parental involvement	Mediation; Parent Collaboration	Restorative Dialogue and Parent Involvement
T3	"I used positive reinforcement always... give good feedbacks... once you touched their heart, they will become a good student."	Positive reinforcement; encouragement; emotional support	Reinforcement	Positive Reinforcement and Emotional Encouragement
T4	"Taking parent conference and talking privately with the students."	Parent conference; private discussion	Communication Strategy	Restorative Dialogue and Parent Involvement
T5	"I offer positive reinforcement for good behavior."	Positive reinforcement	Reinforcement	Positive Reinforcement and Recognition
T6	"Create positive and supportive atmosphere... set clear rules... engaging activities... recognizing good behavior... collaboration and open communication."	Clear rules; engagement; recognition; collaboration	Structured Environment	Structured and Supportive Classroom Environment
T8	"Discuss classroom rules... varied teaching strategies... avoid favoritism... listen to personal issues."	Rule-setting; varied strategies; fairness; empathy	Differentiation; Fairness	Differentiated and Fair Classroom Practices
T9	"Since day 1 I set classroom rules and consequences... taught hand gestures for classroom management."	Early rule-setting; consequences; non-verbal cues	Preventive Strategy	Proactive and Preventive Classroom Management

Table 7. Coping strategies of secondary school teachers in addressing challenges encountered in classroom management

The thematic analysis revealed four major themes: (1) Positive Reinforcement and Recognition, (2) Restorative Dialogue and Parent Involvement, (3) Structured and Proactive Classroom Management, and (4) Relationship-Based and Fair Practices.

The most dominant theme emerging from the data is Positive Reinforcement and Recognition. Several respondents (T3, T5, T6) emphasized giving praise, positive feedback, and emotional encouragement to promote good behavior. Teachers believe that recognizing positive actions strengthens student motivation and builds a supportive classroom atmosphere. Another notable theme is Restorative Dialogue and Parent Involvement (T1, T2, T4). Teachers highlighted the importance of addressing behavior privately, listening to both sides, mediating conflicts, and involving parents when necessary. This reflects a restorative approach that focuses on communication rather than public punishment.

The theme of Structured and Proactive Classroom Management (T6, T7, T9) underscores the importance of setting clear rules and consequences at the beginning of the school year. Teachers emphasized consistency, calm correction, and preventive measures such as non-verbal signals.

Lastly, Relationship-Based and Fair Practices (T7, T8) highlight building rapport, avoiding favoritism, and understanding students' personal concerns. Teachers recognize that fairness and empathy contribute to maintaining respect and discipline.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers rely on proactive, relational, and reinforcement-based strategies rather than punitive measures alone.

The results suggest that teachers adopt a combination of preventive, restorative, and motivational strategies to address behavioral problems. Positive reinforcement appears central, indicating that teachers prioritize encouraging desirable behaviors over punishing misconduct.

Private correction and mediation reflect an effort to preserve student dignity while maintaining authority. The emphasis on early rule-setting demonstrates recognition that structured environments prevent future misbehavior.

The focus on rapport-building and fairness indicates that teachers view classroom management as relational rather than purely disciplinary. These strategies suggest a shift toward supportive and values-based approaches in classroom management.

The prominence of Positive Reinforcement supports the findings of Rafi et al. (2020) and Maisarah (2024), who emphasized that praise and verbal reinforcement significantly improve student motivation and behavior. Similarly, Basnet (2022) found that consistent positive feedback enhances student cooperation and engagement.

The emphasis on clear rules and structured routines aligns with Atmaja (2024) and Khan et al. (2021), who highlighted that structured classroom routines improve behavioral consistency and reduce disruptions.

The focus on restorative dialogue and relationship-building supports Weber et al. (2021) and Kapembwa et al. (2021), who found that restorative practices and peer mediation strengthen accountability and improve classroom climate.

Furthermore, the recognition of individual differences and fairness aligns with Putri et al. (2024) and Bekong (2023), who emphasized that values-based and inclusive strategies enhance student discipline in Catholic school settings.

However, while literatures highlight the effectiveness of these strategies in improving behavioral outcomes, earlier findings in this study revealed persistent challenges such as disengagement and repeated misconduct. This suggests that although teachers are applying evidence-based strategies, consistent implementation and contextual adaptation remain essential for long-term effectiveness.

The qualitative findings reveal that secondary school teachers use positive reinforcement, restorative dialogue, structured rule-setting, relationship-building, and parent involvement as primary strategies in addressing student behavior problems. These approaches reflect proactive, supportive, and values-based classroom management practices. The findings suggest that strengthening consistency, preventive measures, and collaborative partnerships with parents may further enhance behavioral outcomes in Catholic secondary schools.

Part VI. Developed Classroom Management Guidebook Based on the Findings of the Study

The primary output of this research study is the development of a Classroom Management Guidebook intended for secondary school teachers in the Gumaca Catholic Schools Association. This guidebook was formulated based on the study's findings, which revealed that while classroom management practices significantly influence academic outcomes, behavioral concerns require a more structured, consistent, and developmentally responsive framework. In response, the guidebook serves as a research-based and faith-centered intervention designed to standardize classroom management practices, strengthen restorative discipline, and enhance both academic performance and character formation among learners.

The guidebook aims to improve the consistency, effectiveness, and formative impact of classroom management practices by providing teachers with a unified and coherent framework. It guides educators in implementing consistent, fair, and value-oriented strategies across all secondary levels. Moreover, it is designed not only as a practical reference but also as an institutional guide and a professional development resource for educators committed to holistic student formation.

The proposed Classroom Management Guidebook is composed of several key components. First, it presents the Foundations of Catholic Classroom Management, which are grounded in established theoretical frameworks such as Behavioral Learning Theory, Social Learning Theory, Ecological Systems Theory, Restorative Justice Theory, and Self-Determination Theory. These theories collectively integrate reinforcement strategies, teacher modeling, environmental considerations, restorative approaches, and principles of student motivation. This section is supported by study's findings indicating that classroom management practices moderately affect learners' academic outcomes.

Second, the guidebook highlights Faith-Integrated Discipline, particularly through daily faith integration. Findings of the study reveal a slightly lower mean in the integration of biblical stories (3.96), categorized as “often practiced,” indicating an area for further enhancement. This component emphasizes embedding Gospel values into classroom routines and disciplinary practices, ensuring that moral formation is consistently incorporated into daily instruction.

Third, the guidebook introduces a Positive Reinforcement System through a Three-Tier Reinforcement Framework. This includes Tier 1 (daily affirmations), Tier 2 (structured recognition), and Tier 3 (collaboration with parents to support long-term growth). Qualitative findings further support that positive reinforcement and recognition significantly improve student motivation and engagement, although challenges such as limited parental involvement and time constraints were identified.

Fourth, the guidebook emphasizes Structured and Engaging Classroom Routines, highlighting the importance of establishing clear rules, consistent daily routines, and effective engagement strategies. Findings indicate that proactive classroom management, particularly the establishment of rules and consequences at the beginning of the school year, plays a crucial role in sustaining academic success.

Fifth, the guidebook presents Restorative and Responsive Discipline through a “Spectrum of Response,” which organizes restorative practices into a step-by-step framework. This approach ensures consistency and efficiency while preserving student dignity, promoting accountability, and rebuilding relationships within the school community. Rather than relying solely on punitive measures, this framework encourages restorative dialogue and highlights the importance of addressing behavioral concerns privately, as emphasized in the qualitative findings of the study.

Sixth, the guidebook addresses Common Behavioral Concerns by providing targeted and differentiated interventions. These interventions are aligned with findings that identified classroom disruptions, student disengagement, resistance, and repeated rule violations as common issues.

Seventh, the guidebook incorporates Developmentally Responsive Strategies aimed at helping adolescents thrive in the classroom. These strategies focus on addressing the unique developmental needs of early adolescents, particularly during transitional stages in secondary education. Findings of the study indicate that behavioral outcomes are influenced by external and developmental factors beyond classroom strategies, highlighting the importance of this component.

Finally, the guidebook includes a Monitoring and Evaluation Framework, which underscores the importance of assessing classroom management practices using measurable indicators such as student behavior, attendance, academic performance, and engagement. It also encourages continuous reflection and improvement through teacher feedback, as supported by qualitative findings.

Overall, the implementation of this guidebook is expected to result in reduced disciplinary incidents, improved attendance, sustained academic performance, increased student engagement, and strengthened school-home collaboration. By promoting systematic communication and partnership among teachers, parents, and administrators, the guidebook supports the effective management of both academic and behavioral concerns. Ultimately, it aims to foster structured, restorative, and value-oriented learning environments that contribute to the holistic development of students.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study was undertaken to examine how classroom management strategies practiced by secondary school teachers in Gumaca Catholic Schools Association relate to learners’ academic and behavioral outcomes. As Catholic education aims not only to promote academic excellence but also to nurture character formation grounded in Gospel values, understanding the effectiveness of classroom management practices within this context was essential.

The results showed that teachers consistently implemented classroom management strategies anchored in Catholic values, positive reinforcement, structured routines, and restorative practices. These strategies were systematically integrated into classroom instruction and daily interactions, reflecting strong alignment with the mission of Catholic education.

The findings further established that classroom management strategies significantly influenced learners’ academic outcomes. Structured routines, consistent expectations, positive reinforcement, and restorative approaches contributed to maintaining an environment conducive to learning, thereby supporting academic achievement. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that classroom management strategies do not significantly affect learners’ academic outcomes was rejected.

However, classroom management strategies did not demonstrate a statistically significant effect on learners’ behavioral outcomes. This suggests that while effective management supports academic performance, student behavior is shaped by

broader developmental, emotional, familial, and environmental factors beyond classroom practices alone. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that classroom management strategies do not significantly affect learners' behavioral outcomes was accepted.

The qualitative findings reinforced this conclusion by revealing that behavioral issues were multifaceted. Disruptive Behavior, peer conflict, disengagement, emotional concerns, and contextual influences such as parental supervision and technology use contributed to disciplinary concerns.

Taken together, the study indicates that classroom management in Catholic secondary schools is strong and values-driven, effectively supporting academic outcomes. However, addressing behavioral outcomes requires a more holistic and collaborative approach that extends beyond classroom-level interventions to include family engagement, guidance services, and developmentally responsive programs.

In light of the findings that classroom management strategies significantly influenced learners' academic outcomes but did not demonstrate a statistically significant effect on behavioral outcomes, several practical recommendations are proposed to strengthen classroom practice, policy implementation, and future research within Catholic secondary schools.

In view of the study results, several strategic and practice-oriented recommendations are proposed to enhance classroom management, strengthen learner development, and guide policy and future research initiatives within Catholic secondary schools. These recommendations emphasize sustaining effective practices, addressing identified gaps, and fostering collaboration among key educational stakeholders.

1. Sustaining Classroom Management Practices

Findings revealed that secondary school teachers consistently and effectively practiced classroom management strategies such as incorporating Catholic values, positive reinforcement, creating routines, and restorative practices. Teachers are encouraged to sustain the consistently high implementation of classroom management strategies while further refining these approaches to ensure continued effectiveness and responsiveness to learners' needs.

The integration of Catholic values may remain central to classroom instruction and discipline. Educators may deepen this integration by embedding Christian virtues such as respect, compassion, responsibility, and justice into daily learning activities, reflective exercises, and service-oriented tasks that allow students to practice moral decision-making in authentic contexts. Establishing clear behavioral expectations anchored in Catholic teachings may further strengthen character formation.

Positive reinforcement practices may likewise be maintained. Teachers may continue acknowledging effort, perseverance, and improvement through verbal affirmation and constructive feedback while gradually shifting toward strategies that cultivate intrinsic motivation, self-regulation, and personal goal-setting to promote sustainable academic and behavioral growth.

Structured routines and classroom procedures may remain consistent to support smooth transitions and maximize instructional time. Providing students with shared responsibilities in managing classroom processes may encourage accountability and leadership. Periodic review of these routines is recommended to ensure that they remain meaningful and supportive of learning outcomes.

Restorative approaches to discipline may be further strengthened through systematic and consistent application. Teachers may provide structured opportunities for dialogue, mediation, and reflection so that learners develop empathy, accountability, and conflict-resolution skills, thereby fostering healthier classroom relationships.

2. Strengthening Learner Outcomes

Findings indicated that learners demonstrated very satisfactory academic outcomes and generally positive behavioral manifestations across most value domains. To sustain learners' academic performance, teachers should continue implementing organized, engaging, and well-managed learning environments characterized by clear expectations, consistent discipline, and purposeful instructional strategies. Early identification of learners experiencing academic difficulties, accompanied by timely intervention and support, may further maintain high achievement levels.

Given that behavioral development is influenced by factors beyond classroom practices, schools should adopt a more holistic and collaborative approach. Partnerships among teachers, parents, guidance counselors, and administrators may

help ensure consistency in behavioral expectations across contexts. School-wide character formation initiatives and community engagement activities may also reinforce positive values and behaviors beyond the classroom.

3. Broadening Interventions for Behavioral Development

Findings revealed that classroom management strategies did not have a statistically significant effect on learners' behavioral outcomes, suggesting that behavior development is influenced by multiple external factors. Since classroom management alone may not sufficiently influence behavioral outcomes, schools are encouraged to consider broader determinants such as family environment, peer relationships, and school climate. Efforts to strengthen teacher-student relationships, foster open communication, and create supportive learning environments may contribute to improved behavioral adjustment. Additional interventions that address socio-emotional development and character education may complement classroom-level strategies.

4. Addressing Classroom Management Challenges

Findings from the qualitative data revealed that teachers encounter challenges such as student defiance, aggression, bullying, absenteeism, and classroom disengagement. To respond to commonly observed concerns such as defiance, aggression, bullying, absenteeism, and disengagement, schools may implement proactive and preventive measures. Early intervention programs, particularly for students in early adolescence, are recommended. Strengthened collaboration between teachers and guidance counselors may ensure timely support for students experiencing emotional or behavioral difficulties. Clear and consistently enforced policies on bullying prevention and responsible technology use may further reduce recurring disciplinary issues.

5. Improving Teacher Capacity in Managing Behavior

Findings indicated that teachers rely on various coping strategies such as proactive discipline techniques, positive reframing, and collaborative support to manage classroom challenges. Teachers may benefit from adopting varied and interactive instructional approaches that enhance student engagement and attention. Strategies that strengthen teacher-student rapport, promote active participation, and address diverse learning needs may help reduce disruption and disengagement. Ongoing professional development, mentoring, and peer support systems may also enhance teachers' confidence and effectiveness in handling complex classroom situations.

For Secondary School Teachers

Teachers may sustain the integration of values-based instruction, positive reinforcement, structured routines, and restorative practices through reflective teaching and collaboration with colleagues. Differentiated and engagement-centered strategies may be employed to address short attention spans and academic disengagement. In addition, teachers are encouraged to strengthen communication with parents by providing regular feedback on students' academic and behavioral progress. Coordinating with families regarding classroom expectations, study habits, and behavior management strategies may help ensure consistency between school and home environments. The development of a classroom management guidebook grounded in the study's findings is recommended to promote consistency and shared best practices across classrooms.

For Students

Schools may strengthen programs that encourage active participation, peer accountability, and value formation. Leadership opportunities, service-learning projects, and value-driven co-curricular activities may enhance responsibility, discipline, and holistic growth, particularly in areas related to civic and patriotic engagement. Students may also be encouraged to practice self-regulation and responsible use of technology both in school and at home, fostering habits that support academic focus and positive behavior.

For School Administrators and Educational Leaders

Administrators are encouraged to establish school-wide positive behavior support systems that complement classroom initiatives. Institutionalizing professional development programs on adolescent development, restorative practices, and mental health awareness may equip teachers with advanced competencies in addressing behavioral concerns. They may also validate the classroom management guide book before using it in Gumaca Catholic Schools. Structured transition programs for incoming Grade 7 learners may also support adjustment during early adolescence. Moreover, schools may design parent engagement programs, seminars, or workshops that equip families with effective strategies in managing student behavior, reinforcing values, and supporting academic routines at home.

For Parents and Guardians

Home-school collaboration may be strengthened to ensure consistent behavioral expectations and support systems. Parents are encouraged to establish structured home routines such as designated study time, clear household responsibilities, and regulated gadget use to promote discipline and time management. Parent education activities may focus on positive discipline, monitoring technology use, and fostering learners' emotional well-being. Providing positive reinforcement at home, such as acknowledging good behavior and academic effort, may further motivate learners. Active parental involvement, including maintaining open communication with teachers and participating in school activities, may reinforce values formation and continuity between home and school environments.

For the Department of Education and Policymakers

Values-based and restorative classroom management approaches may be integrated into teacher preparation programs and policy frameworks. Broader behavior intervention guidelines that incorporate character education, family engagement, and holistic development may benefit both Catholic and non-Catholic institutions. Policies that promote stronger parent-school partnerships may also enhance the effectiveness of classroom management practices.

For Future Researchers

Future investigations may examine additional variables influencing behavioral outcomes, including socio-emotional competence, peer dynamics, parental involvement, and school climate. Longitudinal and multi-site studies may provide deeper insights into the long-term impact of values-based classroom management. The use of mixed-methods designs is encouraged to generate comprehensive and contextually grounded findings.

In addition, future researchers are encouraged to incorporate classroom observation **methods** to examine learners' behavior in real-time settings directly. Observational techniques, such as structured or non-participant classroom observation, may provide richer and more objective data on student behavior, including attention span, peer interactions, classroom disruptions, and responses to management strategies. This approach may complement self-reported data from teachers and allow for a more comprehensive understanding of classroom dynamics. Furthermore, integrating observation tools or behavior checklists may enhance the validity of findings and provide deeper insights into how classroom management strategies are implemented and experienced by learners in actual classroom environments.

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References

- Ahmad, M., Siddique, A. R., & Arshad, A. (2020). Teacher-student interaction management: A study on the practices and principles in a Pakistani ESL classroom. *The Independent Journal of Teaching and Learning*, 15(2), 51–68. <https://doi.org/10.17159/ijtl.v15i2.19856>
- Afalla, B. T., & Fabelico, F. L. (2020). Sustaining academic success through effective classroom management. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 8(4), 213–221. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2020.8422>
- Age, M. Y. C., & Dhey, B. (2024). Improving learning outcomes of Catholic religious education through storytelling. *Jurnal Syntax Transformation*, 5(3), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.46799/jst.v5i3.1234>
- Atmaja, D. R., & Putri, W. A. (2024). The effect of employee relations and transformational leadership on job satisfaction: The mediating role of interpersonal trust in colleagues and managers. *Journal of Business and Behavioural Entrepreneurship*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.21009/JOBBE.008.2.09>
- Batool, S., Bhatti, R. U., & Waseem, M. (2023). Classroom management strategies and academic achievement. *Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 4(2), 14–24. <https://doi.org/10.52223/jess.2023.4214>
- Bekong, T. (2023). Conflict management strategies in Catholic schools. *American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations*, 5(8), 34–42. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajmei/Volume05Issue08-04>
- Bernal, H., Gumaru, R. C. R., & Oleo, S. T. (2020). Academic performance differences in private and public schools. *Randwick International of Education and Linguistics Science Journal*, 1(3), 253–260. <https://doi.org/10.47175/rielsj.v1i3.135>
- Bialik, M., Bogan, M., Fadel, C., & Horvathova, M. (2022). *Character education for the 21st century*. Center for Curriculum Redesign.
- Bual, J. M. (2021). Teacher leadership in Catholic schools. In *Proceedings of the SEAAIR Conference 2021*.
- Bual, J. M., & Madrigal, D. V. (2021). School climate and teacher leadership. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 21(4), 22–34. <https://doi.org/10.9734/AJESS/2021/v21i430514>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (6th ed.). SAGE.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Schachner, A. C. W., Wojcikiewicz, S. K., Flook, L., Cantor, P., & Osher, D. (2022). Science of learning and development: Educating teachers to support the whole child. *Applied Developmental Science*, 26(2), 97–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2022.2145976>
- Durisic, M. (2022). School climate and student behavioral problems. *Journal of Education and Culture Studies*, 6(3), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.22158/jecs.v6n3p34>
- Freeman, J., Simonsen, B., Briere, D. E., & MacSuga-Gage, A. S. (2014). Pre-service teacher training in classroom management: A review of state accreditation policy and teacher preparation programs. *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 37(2), 106–120. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0888406413507002>
- Ginting, D., Sembiring, R., & Manalu, J. (2022). Teacher competence and student behavior. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 12(1), 67–80. <https://doi.org/10.5590/JERAP.2022.12.1.05>
- Gruijters, R. J., Behrman, J. A., & Raabe, I. J. (2020). Learning inequality in Francophone Africa: School quality and the educational achievement of rich and poor children. *Sociology of Education*, 93(3), 256–276. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038040720919379>
- Gruijters, R. J., Raabe, I. J., & Hübner, N. (2024). Socio-emotional skills and the socioeconomic achievement gap. *Sociology of Education*, 97(2), 120–147. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00380407231216424>
- Haydon, T., Conroy, M. A., Scott, T. M., Sindelar, P. T., & Marchant, M. (2021). Peer-mediated strategies: A review of evidence-based practices to support students with disabilities. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 56(5), 291–298. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1053451220959380>
- Iqbal, A., Munir, F., & Nawaz, F. (2021). Classroom management practices. *Global Educational Studies Review*, 6(2), 45–56. [https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2021\(VI-II\).05](https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2021(VI-II).05)
- Johnson, R. B., & Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2004). Mixed methods research: A research paradigm whose time has come. *Educational Researcher*, 33(7), 14–26. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X033007014>

- Jimerson, S. R. (2022). Effective classroom management to support elementary students: Promoting student success through reducing off-task problem behaviors. *Current Research in Psychology and Behavioral Science*, 3(7), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.54026/crpbs/1067>
- Khasinah, S., Nurdin, S., & Panjaitan, A. M. (2024). Managing classroom: Teachers' strategies and challenges. *PIONIR: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 13(2), 24–37. <https://doi.org/10.22373/pjp.v13i2.24134>
- Kumari, S., & Biswas, B. (2024). Values-based education: A pathway to holistic development. *International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies*, 4(1), 168–174.
- Larsen, S. A., Forbes, A. Q., Little, C. W., Alaba, S. H., & Coventry, W. L. (2022). The public-private debate: School sector differences in academic achievement from Year 3 to Year 9. *Australian Educational Researcher*, 49(2), 395–414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-021-00498-w>
- Lynch, J., O'Donoghue, G., & Peiris, C. L. (2022). Classroom movement breaks and physically active learning are feasible, reduce sedentary behaviour and fatigue, and may increase focus in university students: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(13), 7775. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19137775>
- Maisarah, M. (2024). Enhancing children's learning motivation through positive reinforcement: A classroom communication strategy. *Journal Smart*, 10(1), 81–95.
- Mamaile, D., & Omodan, B. I. (2023). Exploring challenges hindering teachers' implementation of classroom management strategies in Gauteng High Schools, South Africa. *Research in Educational Policy and Management*, 5(2), 245–262. <https://doi.org/10.46303/repam.2023.22>
- Muderedzwa, (2021). Socioeconomic and institutional determinants of student academic performance in Zimbabwean secondary schools. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 5(7), 123–132. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2021.5709>
- Nafisah, Z., Nafiah, N., Hidayat, M. T., & Hartatik, S. (2020). Meta analysis of the effect of classroom management on student learning outcomes in elementary schools. *Primary: Jurnal Pendidikan Guru Sekolah Dasar*, 9(4), 504–512. <https://doi.org/10.33578/jpkip.v9i4.7984>
- Noor, S., Ali, A., & Hashmi, M. A. (2023). Effects of teachers' conflict management techniques on the learning environment in the classroom. *Global Social Sciences Review*, VIII(1), 481–489. [https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2023\(VIII-1\).45](https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2023(VIII-1).45)
- Omodan, B. I., & Mamaile, D. (2024). The roles of teachers in enhancing effective classroom management strategies in Gauteng high schools, South Africa. *Nurture*, 18(3), 573–586. <https://doi.org/10.55951/nurture.v18i3.682>
- Oparaugo, U., Onwurrah, C., Nwanguma, V., & Ali, L. (2024). Classroom management as correlate of students' behavioural outcome in junior secondary schools in Ishielu Local Government Area, Ebonyi State. *EIKI Journal of Effective Teaching Methods*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.59652/jetm.v2i2.202>
- Owusu, G. M. Y., Mensah, J. K., & Boateng, R. (2021). Reinforcement strategies in classroom management: Perspectives from Ghanaian teachers. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 9(11), 71–80. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5724530>
- Patampang, C., Tandiangga, P., & Palinoan, F. F. (2024). The effect of teacher leadership and school climate on students' learning outcomes. *JPPI (Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Indonesia)*, 10(2), 32–39. <https://doi.org/10.29210/020243210>
- Putri, A. T., & Laili, M. (2024). An analysis of classroom management conducted by the English teacher at a private Islamic junior high school. *Edunesia: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan*, 5(3), 1449–1463. <https://doi.org/10.51276/edu.v5i3.996>
- Rafi, A., Ansar, A., & Sami, M. A. (2020). The implication of positive reinforcement strategy in dealing with disruptive behaviour in the classroom: A scoping review. *Journal of Rawalpindi Medical College*, 24(2), 173–179. <https://doi.org/10.37939/jrmc.v24i2.1190>
- Safiullah, Nadeem, H. A., & Asma. (2023). Impact of classroom management on students' academic achievement at secondary school level in Peshawar. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 3(2), 19–26. <https://doi.org/10.54183/jssr.v3i2.208>
- Simpson, J. N., Hopkins, S., Eakle, C. D., & Rose, C. A. (2020). Implement today! Behavior management strategies to increase engagement and reduce challenging behaviors in the classroom. *Beyond Behavior*, 29(2), 119–128. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1074295620909448>
- Simuyaba, E., & Kapembwa, R. (2021). Examining how the nature and perceived benefits of school-based restorative practices influence positive behaviour in deviant pupils: A case of selected secondary schools of Kabwe District, Zambia. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 5(9), 234–243. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2021.5928>
- Sultmann, W., McCluskey, G., Renshaw, P., & McKellar, S. (2024). Restorative practices in education: Improving classroom management and student relationships. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 28(10), 1125–1142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2023.2177325>
- Twenge, J. M. (2023). *Generations: The real differences between Gen Z, Millennials, Gen X, Boomers, and Silents—and what they mean for America's future*. Simon & Schuster.
- Weber, C., Rehder, M., & Vereenoghe, L. (2021). Student-reported classroom climate pre and post teacher training in restorative practices. *Frontiers in Education*, 6, 719357. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2021.719357>

- Waweru, S. N., & Gacheri, N. P. (2021). Influence of classroom behaviour management practices on students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Tharaka Nithi County, Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Social Science Research*, 4(5), 166–174. <https://doi.org/10.37500/IJESSR.2021.4512>
- Xu, C., Zhu, K., & Liu, S. (2023). Classroom management strategies, practices, and learners' academic performance. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 23(8), 18–35. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13315676>
- Yousuf, M. M., Shaheen, N., Kheri, N. A., & Fatma, G. (2023). Exploring effective classroom management techniques in English teaching. *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, 11(11), 382–393. <https://doi.org/10.17762/ijritcc.v11i11.9772>

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.